

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report presents the evaluation of tropical cyclone representation in SR-ESMs.

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WP7

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Executive summary

It is anticipated that global storm-resolving models will simulate realistic tropical cyclones (TC), but sensitivities to resolution, coupling, model physics (such as treatment of deep convection) are yet to be quantified. Additionally, km-scale models open opportunities to study key processes in cyclone development, including interactions with the near-surface ocean. This report compiles key findings on the topic of tropical cyclones. nextGEMS simulations show good qualitative agreement with observations in terms of the total TC frequency and the seasonality globally, although biases exist in particular basins. nextGEMS models capture realistic intensification rates, including rapid intensification, which remains challenging even in initialised forecasts, and this is sensitive to whether or not deep convection is parameterised. The simulated relationship between intensification rate and cyclone inner-core size resembles the observed relationship, indicating that GSRMs may help understand what role, if any, size has in determining intensification rate. Cyclones interacting with cold-core eddies exhibit significantly lower intensities and intensification rates, but TCs encountering warm-core eddies tend to show higher intensities and intensification rates. Under SSP3-7.0, frequency changes of TCs up to category-four-equivalent intensity are small, but TCs with peak intensities of at least 50 ms^{-1} (equivalent to category five) exhibit a marked increase in frequency. This result is qualitatively similar to existing findings, but greater confidence may be drawn here, as nextGEMS explicitly resolve the strongest intensities. Under warming, nextGEMS models project stronger western North Pacific TCs and altered TC-rainfall patterns, particularly a delay in peak TC precipitation. It will be important to build on this result in future work to explore sensitivities to model physics as well as alternative scenarios. The impact of ocean spin-up on basin-scale and global TC activity warrants further investigation to first address the issue of short spin-up affecting weaker TC frequency and second to address the potential impact on climate projections.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP7	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify the importance of meso-scale air-sea interaction on tropical climate, on its dominant patterns of variability and teleconnections, and on its response to global warming (O1,O2)	yes
To appraise the significance of resolving atmospheric convection and storm-scales for simulating the West African Monsoon (WAM) and hydrological cycle extremes, and their response to global warming (O1,O2)	no
To evaluate the influence of mesoscales on tropical cyclones and on their response to global warming. (O2)	yes
To assess the impacts of climate and climate change on global primary productivity, and global and West African fisheries using SR-ESMs (O1,O2,O3)	no
To anticipate the relevance of resolving mesoscale circulations for global climate change assessments (O1,O2,O3)	yes
To evaluate and refine new ocean mixed layer and planetary boundary layer representation in the coupled system (O1)	no

Synergies

This deliverable (D7.2) creates synergies with deliverables D7.1 and D7.4, as follows:

In D7.1, the representation of African Easterly Waves (AEW) was evaluated. AEWs impose synoptic-scale variability in West African Monsoon and are known to provide the seeds for the genesis of tropical cyclones in the North Atlantic region. For other regions, D7.1 work on ENSO variability, the leading mode of global multi-annual climate variability, has implications of simulated tropical cyclone activity, particularly how well basin-scale inter-annual variability and seasonality are represented.

In D7.1, analysis of the representation of the planetary boundary layer in stratocumulus cloud regions was presented. Additionally, D7.1 and D7.4 also present results concerning ocean mixing and the representation of the upper-most layer of the ocean, both of which are important for tropical cyclone development and intensification. An analysis of developments in planetary boundary layer and ocean mixed layer schemes is presented in D7.4.

1 Introduction

Tropical cyclones (TCs) are the most economically costly synoptic-scale meteorological phenomenon (World Meteorological Organization (2021)), containing mesoscale and convective-scale updrafts, eyewalls and rainbands. New analyses highlight an increasing trend in their destructiveness over recent decades (Elsner (2020); Klotzbach et al. (2022)) and the disproportionately high exposure of socioeconomically underprivileged populations to TC hazards globally (Jing et al. (2024)). Simulating realistic TCs is therefore a vital ambition in weather and climate modelling. The physical processes governing a TC's lifecycle are relatively well understood, but many of these processes occur at scales below those resolved by global climate models. This undermines our understanding of TC risk and precludes reliable predictions of TC behaviour in a warming climate. A key aspect of current climate model development for simulating TCs is increased horizontal resolution in both the atmosphere and ocean (Kreussler et al. (2021); Roberts et al. (2020); Vannire et al. (2020)). State-of-the-art models, whose resolutions are approaching the kilometre scale, are termed global storm-resolving models (GSRMs; Satoh et al. (2019)). It is anticipated that such resolutions—nominally <10 km—resolve many of the physical processes important for cyclogenesis and cyclone intensification (Judt et al. (2021)).

Global climate models with horizontal resolutions of 1 degree fail to capture TC frequency (Roberts et al. (2020)), intensity (Davis (2018)), and wind structure (Vannire et al. (2020)). Increasing resolution from 1 to 0.25 degrees—now typical in global modelling—improves simulated TC characteristics, but intensity remains significantly underestimated (Roberts et al. (2020)). Furthermore, simulated intensification rates are too slow (Davis (2018)) and rapid intensification (RI) of TCs, defined as the 95th percentile of 24-hour intensity changes (Kaplan and DeMaria (2003)), is not captured by coarse models. These shortcomings are also true of the latest, similar-resolution reanalyses (Aarons et al. (2021); Dulac et al. (2024)). Capturing RI is particularly important because most of the strongest TCs undergo RI (Lee et al., 2016), yet forecast errors are typically several times larger for RI than non-RI cases (Majumdar et al. (2023); Trabing and Bell (2020)). Hurricane Otis (October 2023), for example, intensified by 74 ms^{-1} —from tropical storm to category 5—in under 24 hours prior to landfall, but this was not forecast by any operational model (Garca-Franco et al. (2024)). In forecasting, initialisation and assimilation of observational data aid model realism, but insufficient resolution contributes to intensity errors (Tam et al. (2021)). GSRMs, run at resolutions akin to those of current operational forecasts, may help understand models' capabilities at these scales without initialisation. In particular, model deficiencies may result from not capturing the observed association of the highest intensification rates with smaller TC inner-core size (Sparks and Toumi (2022); Xu and Y. Wang (2015)) and not representing inner-core processes (Trabing and Bell, 2020)—both require high atmospheric resolution (Moon et al. (2020)). RI is expected to occur more frequently in a warmer climate (Bhatia et al. (2022)), so the scientific and societal rationales for simulating realistic intensification rates are equally compelling.

Judt et al. (2021) analysed TCs in 40-day, atmosphere-only GSRM simulations and found that km-scale models exhibit disparate frequency, intensity, size, and structure biases. As noted by Judt et al. (2021), longer simulations are needed to draw general conclusions about simulated TC characteristics, and there is a need to assess storm-resolving resolution in the fully coupled system, as atmosphere-only models simulate more intense TCs because ocean feedbacks,

IFS (ECMWF)			ICON (MPI-M)		
Lang et al., 2023 Rackow et al., 2025			Hohenegger et al., 2023 Koldunov et al., 2023		
Simulation length	Atmosphere	Ocean	Simulation name, length	Atmosphere	Ocean
Cycle 2 (47r3)			Cycle 2 (native)		
2 years	9 km, deep on	NEMO, 0.25°	ngc2013, 17 years	10 km, explicit	ICON-O
1 year	4.4 km, deep off	FESOM 2.1, 5 km	ngc2012, 8 years	10 km, explicit	ICON-O
8 months	2.8 km, deep off	FESOM 2.1, 5 km	ngc2009, 2.5 years	5 km, explicit	ICON-O
Cycle 3 (48r1)			Cycle 3 (HEALPix)		
5 years	28 km, deep on	NEMO 3.4, 0.25°	ngc3028, 5 years	z=8, 24 km, explicit	ICON-O
5 years	9 km, deep on	NEMO 3.4, 0.25°	ngc3028, 5 years	z=10, 6 km, explicit	ICON-O
1 year	9 km, deep off	NEMO 3.4, 0.25°	Cycle 4 (HEALPix)		
1 year	9 km, deep, shallow off	NEMO 3.4, 0.25°	ngc4008, 30 years	z=9, 12 km, explicit	ICON-O
1 year	9 km, 1/6 M _b	NEMO 3.4, 0.25°	ngc4009 30 years	5 km, explicit	ICON-O
1 year	9 km, deep on	FESOM 2.5, 5 km	Cycle 5 (HEALPix)		
5 years	4.4 km, 1/6 M _b	FESOM 2.5, 5 km	ngc5004, 2 years	2.5 km, explicit	ICON-O
Cycle 4 (48r1, HEALPix)					
30 years, SSP3-7.	9 km, 1/6 M _b	FESOM 2.5, 5 km			
30 years, historical	9 km, 1/6 M _b	FESOM 2.5, 5 km			
14 months	2.8 km, 1/6 M _b	FESOM 2.5, 5 km			
14 months	2.8 km, deep off	FESOM 2.5, 5 km			

Figure 1: Model-development (cycles 2 and 3) and production (cycle 4) simulations produced in nextGEMS with ECMWF's Integrated Forecast System (Lang et al. (2023); Rackow et al. (2025)) and MPI-M's Icosahedral non-Hydrostatic Model (Hohenegger et al. (2023); Koldunov et al. (2023)).

which reduce intensity, are not included (Zarzycki (2016)). In nextGEMS, we analysed TCs simulations performed with two fully coupled GSRMs, spanning resolutions of 28 to 2.8 km in the atmosphere and 28 (0.25 degree) to 5 km (0.04 degree) in the ocean (Segura et al. (2025)). These multi-year simulations from nextGEMS provide opportunities to examine TC realism and processes at storm-resolving scales.

2 Simulations overview

The work presented in this report draws on simulations produced during model-development cycles 2 and 3 and the production cycle 4 (Fig. 1).

3 Results

3.1 Tropical cyclones effected by mesoscale eddies (Arjun Kumar, Nils Brueggemann and Jochem Marotzke, MPI-M)

The next generation of climate models achieves spatial resolutions high enough to directly simulate various dynamical processes that previously had to be parameterized. For example, the atmospheric component of the ICON model in the nextGEMS configuration no longer uses parameterizations for deep convection. As a result, Tropical Cyclones (TCs) are now simulated

using physically based dynamics rather than empirical parameterizations.

On the ocean side, the ICON model in the nextGEMS configuration does not parameterize ocean eddies but instead aims to resolve them explicitly. This enables unique opportunities to simulate the dynamical interactions between single ocean eddies and single tropical cyclones in a global context. Those interactions could previously only be studied regionally or through statistical approaches.

In two studies, we take advantage of these new modeling capabilities to investigate how ocean eddies influence tropical cyclone (TC) intensity using the ICON model. Through a detailed process-based analysis of TC intensity changes, we examine a dedicated case study of a TC–eddy interaction and show that a particular simulated subsurface warm-core ocean eddy that could not be detected from the sea surface temperature can increase TC intensity by one category on the Saffir-Simpson scale (Kumar et al. (2022)). In our example, TC intensity decreases initially due to intrinsic dynamical effects (see Fig. 2), including atmospheric boundary layer processes, reduced surface heat fluxes caused by ocean mixing, and the formation of a cold wake that limits the storm’s energy supply. However, once the TC encounters the warm-core eddy, surface cooling diminishes, latent heat fluxes rise, and the cyclone intensifies again.

In a follow-up study (Kumar et al., submitted), we investigate the extent to which ocean eddies systematically influence tropical cyclone intensity. To this end, we track all TCs and ocean eddies in a one-year nextGEMS simulation with 5 km resolution in both the ocean and atmosphere. Using these tracks, we identify the frequency and duration of TC encounters with warm- and cold-core ocean eddies. Our analysis reveals that TCs interacting with cold-core eddies exhibit significantly lower intensities and intensification rates (see Fig. 3). In contrast, TCs encountering warm-core eddies tend to show higher intensities and intensification rates, although this effect is not statistically significant. Overall, our results suggest that the net effect of ocean eddies is a reduction in global-mean tropical cyclone intensity.

3.2 Estimating the internal variability of tropical cyclone frequency (Mikael Karvinen, Nils Brueggemann and Jochem Marotzke, MPI-M)

A long-standing question in climate science is to what extent tropical cyclone (TC) intensity and frequency will change in response to climate change. Observational records from 1980 to 2020 suggest a slight decline in TC frequency—by approximately 4 to 5 storms per year. However, this signal is embedded in strong interannual variability, and it remains debatable whether the observed trend is statistically significant. In our study (Karvinen et al., in prep.), we use a next-generation coupled climate model with a horizontal resolution of 10km in both the atmosphere and the ocean, run over a 30-year period. The simulation is conducted under constant CO₂ forcing, representative of greenhouse gas levels in the year 2020. As a result, the simulation is largely free of model drift that would otherwise arise from continuously changing greenhouse gas concentrations).

This simulation combines three notable features: (1) it offers significantly higher resolution than typical CMIP-class simulations, (2) it is driven by an idealized, constant CO₂ forcing, and (3) it spans three decades what is long enough to robustly analyze TC statistics. However, the model

Figure 2: Tropical cyclone encountering a sub-surface warm-core eddy. Ocean heat content (a) reveals the eddy while it is invisible from the surface SST (b). Once the TC propagates over the ocean a cold wake establishes (c-d). However, once it encounter the warm-core eddy (e), the surface cooling reduces. The encounter has consequences for the TC intensity (f) which increases once the warm-core eddy (indicated by WF in f) is met. Figure adopted from Kumar et al. (2022)

Figure 3: Time series of hourly data for TC intensity plotted against the time relative to maximum intensity. The black, blue and red curves denote the ensemble averages for neutral, cold and warm tropical cyclones, respectively. TC tracks that encounter cold-core eddies for a longer period have lower intensities. Figure adopted from Kumar et al., submitted.

also exhibits biases in its simulated climate that affect both the frequency and intensity of tropical cyclones. For example, we find that biases in vertical wind shear and background specific humidity can largely explain the spatial biases in TC occurrence. Moreover, the simulation fails to produce any Category 5 TCs and underestimates the number of Category 4 storms, while overestimating the frequency of Category 2 and 3 TCs. This bias is likely linked to the surface wind drag formulation, which unrealistically increases the drag coefficient at high wind speeds, thereby limiting the model's ability to simulate the most intense cyclones.

Despite the deficiencies in TC intensity distribution and spatial biases in TC occurrence, the simulation shows good qualitative agreement with observations in terms of the total tropical cyclone frequency and the seasonality of TC frequency (see Fig. 4). This gives us confidence that the model realistically captures the interannual variability of TC intensity. Using the 30-year time series under constant CO_2 forcing, we compute resampled trends in TC frequency along with their associated standard deviations. Our results indicate that the observed trend (a decrease of approximately 0.1 TCs per year) is not statistically significant and can be attributed to internal variability.

Overall, our research with next-generation climate models suggests that current observational records are insufficient for reliably forecasting tropical cyclone intensities, particularly when influenced by subsurface ocean eddies, or for detecting long-term trends in TC frequency, which are strongly affected by internal variability. Our results highlight the potential of high-resolution, coupled climate models as a powerful tool for advancing future tropical cyclone research.

Figure 4: Tropical cyclone frequency in the ICON simulation (bars) and from the IBTrACS dataset (black line). ICON simulates the TC frequency quite well, however, TCs with category 4 and 5 are underrepresented.

3.3 Tropical cyclone intensity and structure, and the response to warming (Alexander Baker, University of Reading)

Tropical cyclones were tracked in six-hourly nextGEMS data using the feature-tracking algorithm *TempestExtremes* (Ullrich and Zarzycki (2017); Ullrich et al. (2021)). Further details are available in Baker et al. (2024).

3.3.1 Overview of TC activity

IFS and ICON generally simulate realistic global distributions of TCs (Fig. 5), which is particularly evident in longer multi-year simulations. It is notable that IFS simulates lower activity across the North Atlantic compared with observational data, which is a feature of this model that should be explored in future research. ICON, however, overestimates North Atlantic frequency (Fig. 6).

3.3.2 Frequency

Annual-mean TC frequency, n_{TC} , and TC days, d_{TC} , show sensitivity to resolution and differ between IFS and ICON (Fig. 7a, b). In IFS, simulated n_{TC} in both cycle 2 and 3 is closer to observations at higher resolutions, although cycle-2 simulations at 4.4 and 2.8 km span less than one year. However, d_{TC} is underestimated by IFS, due to the presence of shorter-lived TCs. Both models generally underestimate the frequency of t_{TC} in the range 10–17 days. ICON simulates relatively short-lived TCs more frequently than observed, consistent with track density patterns (Fig. 5). t_{TC} therefore exhibits greater sensitivity to whether deep convection is explicit or parameterised than to resolution. The use of reduced cloud-base mass flux versus explicit deep convection at 2.8 km in IFS results in a factor two difference across all three TC activity metrics. Additionally, cycle-3 IFS simulations at 9 km reveal an increase in n_{TC} and d_{TC} with FESOM at 5 km compared with NEMO at 0.25 degree. ICON shows stronger sensitivity to model formulation than to atmospheric resolution: simulated n_{TC} and d_{TC} exceed observational values in cycle 2 but are closer to IBTrACS in cycle 3. Accumulated cyclone energy (ACE), a cumulative measure of TC activity (intensity and frequency), is well simulated in cycle 3 by IFS at 4.4 km but generally overestimated by ICON, and model performance is better globally than for the Northern Hemisphere (7c).

3.3.3 Intensity and intensification rate

A clear distinction between IFS and ICON exists in simulating the relationship between TC minimum central pressure, p_{min} , and near-surface wind speed, v_{max} (Fig. 8). IFS generally captures the observed relationship and shows sensitivity to atmospheric resolution, particularly in cycle 3 and cycle 4: for v_{max} , simulated TCs reach category 2 at 28 km and category 5 at 4.4 km. A caveat is the sample size of intense storms in a five-year simulation may be insufficient to assess significance; the distinct curve of the 2.8-km simulation (cycle 2) is likely due to small sample size. The strongest v_{max} simulated by IFS is 89 ms^{-1} , which ranks among the strongest

Figure 5: Tropical cyclone track density in nextGEMS simulations. Each model and development cycle occupy a column, with increasing atmospheric resolution ordered from top to bottom. Note that IFS (cycle 2) simulations are short and densities are therefore low. Unit is cyclone transits per year.

Figure 6: Tropical cyclone seasonal cycle in nextGEMS simulations. Basins are: North Atlantic (NA), western North Pacific (WP), eastern North Pacific (EP), northern Indian Ocean (NI), South Pacific (SP), southern Indian Ocean (SI), and Australian region (AU). Each TC is assigned to a single basin by its location of maximum intensity.

Figure 7: Annual-mean TC statistics in IBTrACS observations (black) and nextGEMS simulations: (a) TC frequency, n_{TC} , (b) cumulative TC days, d_{TC} , and (c) accumulated cyclone energy (ACE), Σu_{10}^2 , scaled by 10^{-4} . Bars represent global statistics and hatched areas represent the Northern Hemisphere. Tropical depressions (i.e., systems with $v_{max} < 17 \text{ ms}^{-1}$) were excluded. This is an updated version of analysis presented by Baker et al. (2024).

observed TCs. ICON simulates deep systems; the lowest simulated p_{min} is 863 hPa. However, v_{min} is too weak for a given p_{min} , and this model error deteriorates from cycle 2 to cycle 3. Marginal p_{min} distributions also demonstrate this. This is potentially related to the Langmuir turbulence parameterisation used in cycle 3, which slightly deepens the ocean mixed layer, which may impact TC-induced sea-surface cooling (Wu et al. (2018)), as a deeper mixed layer can be associated with weaker TC-induced sea-surface cooling. Two aspects of the observed wind–pressure relationship hamper comparisons with model data. First, observed wind speeds are estimates of maximum sustained gusts, whereas models output instantaneous wind. Second, the representativeness of point-wise observations, including retrievals and estimations, for simulated wind speeds, which are grid-cell averages, is questionable, especially at coarser resolution.

In addition to peak intensity, it is important to analyse intensification rates, including RI. We first composited the temporal evolution of v_{max} and p_{min} for the upper decile of observed and simulated TCs (Fig. 9). IFS exhibits strong sensitivity to resolution. At 28 km (cycle 3), TC intensity increases too slowly and peaks at approximately half the observed value. Simulations at 9 and 10 km are closer to ITrACS. At 4.4 km, IFS mimics observations for composite v_{max} (Fig. 9a) and p_{min} (Fig. 9b). ICON at 5 km (cycle 2) performs well for v_{max} but p_{min} is too low, consistent with Fig. 8. Unexpectedly, ocean model / resolution has little apparent impact in IFS: 9-km simulations with FESOM or NEMO show little difference for v_{max} or p_{min} .

RI is similarly sensitive to atmospheric resolution (Fig. 10). RI ratio, a measure of RI occurrence defined following Bhatia et al. (2022) as the ratio of 24-hour v_{max} changes above the RI threshold to non-RI v_{max} changes, simulated by IFS at 4.4 km (cycle 3) is close to the observed ratio (Fig. 10). In cycle 2, ICON simulates an RI ratio that is almost a factor 2 higher at 5 km than at 10 km, but remains below the observed value, and this metric deteriorates in cycle 3, again potentially due to a deeper mixed layer.

3.3.4 Horizontal structure

Judt et al. (2021) reported variation among GSRMs in representing mean TC size. Here, we assess how realistic simulated inner-core, outer size, and horizontal wind structure are at high resolution, focussing on IFS simulations, which span the largest range in atmospheric resolution available in nextGEMS. Radial profiles of tangential wind speed, v_t , show smaller radius of maximum wind (RMW) with increasing resolution (Fig. 11a). This result confirms the trend described by Vannire et al. (2020) and Moon et al. (2020), who demonstrated a reduction of horizontal inner-core size with resolution increases in the range 1 to 0.25 degrees. Additionally, IFS simulations generally agree with the observed mean RMW across resolutions of 9–2.8 km. Again, little sensitivity to ocean model / resolution is seen between NEMO and FESOM runs with a 9-km atmosphere. Outer TC size, defined as the radius at which $v_t = 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, R_8 , decreases by a factor of 2 between resolutions of 28 and 2.8 km, from 3 to 1.7 degrees (Fig. 11a), and therefore smaller than observational estimates at 2.8 km (Schreck III et al. (2014); Schenkel et al. (2018)). Frequency distributions of R_8 exhibit sensitivity to both resolution and the use of explicit convection: higher resolution reduces mean R_8 , and explicit convection shifts the distribution to lower values (Fig. 11b). Similarly, mean integrated kinetic energy within R_8 , IKE_8 ,

Figure 8: Relationship (second-order polynomial fits) between per-TC v_{max} and p_{min} for IB-TrACS observations (black) and nextGEMS simulations, with marginal v_{max} and p_{min} frequency distributions shown in the top and right-hand panels, respectively (note log scales). TC categories, defined following Klotzbach et al. (2020) and the Saffir–Simpson scale for p_{min} and v_{max} , respectively, are delineated by grey, dashed lines. The legend gives the horizontal atmosphere and ocean resolutions of each simulation. This is an updated version of analysis presented by Baker et al. (2024).

Figure 9: Composite TC intensity lifecycles for IBTrACS observations (black) and nextGEMS simulations, centred on peak v_{max} ($t = 0$), indicated by the grey, dashed line, for (a) v_{max} and (b) p_{min} . Analysis was performed for the upper decile (i.e., most intense by lifetime-maximum intensity) of both observed and simulated TCs. This is an updated version of analysis presented by Baker et al. (2024).

Figure 10: Observed and simulated RI ratio, a measure of RI occurrence, computed for the $15.4 \text{ ms}^{-1} 24\text{h}^{-1}$ threshold. By construction, the IBTrACS RI ratio is 0.05 (i.e., 5 percent). The legend gives the horizontal resolutions of the atmosphere and ocean for each simulation, and bar labels in (d) also give the atmosphere resolution. This is an updated version of analysis presented by Baker et al. (2024).

increases with increased resolution (although means are skewed by small high-IKE TC counts), and the distribution shifts towards higher values with either explicit convection or reduced cloud-base mass flux (Fig. 11c), which increase inner-core v_t (Fig. 11a). At lower resolution, simulated IKE_8 exceeds 100 TJ less frequently at 28 and 9 km than in simulations at 4.4 and 2.8 km. This result differs somewhat from an analysis of models spanning resolutions of 1 to 0.25 degrees (Kreussler et al. (2021)), which revealed IKE to be insensitive to this range in resolution because the larger horizontal size of TCs simulated at 1 degree compensates low wind speeds. Here, however, high-IKE TCs are poorly sampled—note IKE_8 is noisy above 400 TJ (Fig. 11c)—and we are unable to assess significance.

We next investigate the relationship between intensification rate and size. IBTrACS data show an inverse relationship between intensification rate and RMW. IFS simulations at 4.4 and 2.8 km reproduce the observed slope of this relationship, with high intensification rate associated with small RMW (Fig. 11d). 9-km simulations exhibit flatter slopes, and the 28-km simulation fails to capture the relationship, exhibiting a flat slope. The slope is more sensitive to resolution than to whether convection is explicit or parameterised: contrast, for example, cycle-2 simulations at 4.4 and 2.8 km. IFS simulations are offset from observations, indicating that, for a given RMW, the simulated intensification rate tends to be higher than observed. However, this may be partly due to linear fitting: linear fits are shown only to illustrate the scatter for IBTrACS and each simulation, and the relationship between intensification rate and RMW is evidently non-linear (K. T. F. Chan and J. C. L. Chan (2018)). IFS also simulates a similar relationship between the latitude of maximum intensity (LMI) and RMW to that seen in observations (Fig. 11e); the latitudinal dependence of TC size is well captured but insensitive to resolution.

3.3.5 Projected global changes in intensity and intensification rate

GSRMs may offer new insights into aspects of TC behaviour—lifetime-maximum intensity and intensification rate, including RI—that are key to quantifying TC risk yet poorly captured or unresolved in typical climate models. The 30-year, historical IFS simulation captures the observed annual-mean, global frequency distribution of TCs well (Fig. 12a). At 4.4-km resolution, the distribution is also well captured, but annual-mean frequencies of the most intense TCs are somewhat overestimated, with the caveat that the length of this simulation is five years. Reduced cloud-base mass flux appears to be key to this result. The 9-km simulation without reduced cloud-base mass flux—albeit a short, one-year integration—underestimates observed frequencies (Fig. 12a). Under SSP3-7.0, frequency changes of TCs up to category-four-equivalent intensity are small, but TCs with peak intensities of at least 50 ms^{-1} (equivalent to category five) exhibit an increase in frequency that is especially marked when all TC timesteps are considered (Fig. 12b). This result is qualitatively similar to existing findings (Knutson et al. (2020)), and consistent with observed trends (Elsner (2020); Klotzbach et al. (2022)), but quantitative information from GSRMs, which resolve the strongest observed storms, may be more trustworthy, and may avoid the assumption that changes in the upper quantiles of coarse models serves as a proxy for changes in real-world intense TCs. Additional research with other GSRMs is warranted.

IFS overestimates the observed frequency distribution of 24-hour intensification rates (Fig. 12c). However, this analysis was performed for all TC timesteps and therefore model–observation

Figure 11: Horizontal wind structure of TCs. (a) Azimuthal-mean (i.e., radial) profiles of v_t for all TCs with $p_{min} \leq 975$ hPa. The observed mean and standard deviation of RMW are indicated by the black and grey vertical lines, respectively. (b) Distribution of TC size, estimated by R_8 . (c) Distribution of IKE, computed within R_8 . Mean and standard deviation of R_8 and IKE_8 for each simulation are indicated by the jittered points (plotted against the x-axis only), with size scaled by mean v_{max} . (d) Relationship between TC intensification rate ($24h^{-1}$) and RMW, following Xu and Y. Wang (2015). (e) Relationship between LMI and RMW. Linear fits are shown in (d) and (e). The legend gives the horizontal atmosphere and ocean resolutions of each simulation and the number of TCs, n , in each composite profile in (a); shorter simulations in cycle 2 have smaller n . For (b) and (c), all data were regridded to a common resolution of 0.25 degrees. This is an updated version of analysis presented by Baker et al. (2024).

disagreement is magnified by missing IBTrACS data. The simulated frequency distributions are more sensitive to whether reduced cloud-base mass flux is used than to resolution, at least for the range of storm-resolving resolutions considered here. Under SSP3-7.0, frequency changes are minimal, except for an increase in rapid weakening events (Fig. 12d). The simulated wind–pressure relationship in the historical and scenario simulations are very similar (not shown).

3.4 Borneo vortex and SE Asia circulation (Shunya Koseki, University of Bergen)

Borneo vortex is a cyclonic circulation emerging around the Borneo Island (as a rare case, promoting to a typhoon, Chang et al. (2003)) and induces heavy rainfall during winter. Its cyclogenesis is well connected to monsoon cold surge (Chang et al. (2003); Koseki et al. (2014)) and the analysis on the monsoonal cold surges is given in Section 2.4 of D7.1. In this study, following the detection algorithm of Borneo vortex, the methodology of (Koseki et al. (2014)) with a few modifications, we assess the models' performance of representing Borneo vortex. For detecting Borneo vortex, we used $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ interpolated daily data of horizontal winds at 850hPa. Here, we assess how nextGEMS ESMs (ICON-ngc2013, ICON-RTHK001, Segura et al. (2025) and AWI-CM3-HR (IFS-FESOM), Sein et al., 2025 tbs) can reproduce the properties of monsoon cold surges and corresponding rainfall comparing with ERA5 and some CMIP6 ESMs (MIROC6; Tatebe et al. (2019), TaiESM1; Y.-C. Wang et al. (2021), and MRI-ESM2-0; Yukimoto et al. (2019)).

As shown in Fig. 13a, the occurrence of Borneo vortices concentrates around the north-west of the Borneo Island spreading along the winter monsoonal flow in ERA5. Note that because the algorithm in this study simply counts the number of vortex centres from the daily data, the same vortex event might be included several times. The cyclogenesis of Borneo vortex is consistent well with vorticity flux advection along the winter monsoonal flow (e.g., Koseki et al. (2014)). The ICON ESMs can reproduce well the cyclogenesis of Borneo vortex even though ngc2013 tends to generate slightly westward-biased occurrence, and more vortices occur over the Gulf of Thailand (100°E - 105°E and 7°N - 10°N) in RTHK001 than ERA5 and ngc2013 (Figs. 13b and c). Because of a shorter coverage of available daily data of AWI-CM3-HR, the total occurrence is less than ERA5 and the ICON models, but AWI-CM3-HR is also captures a high density of vortices around the Borneo Island (Fig. 13d). Because MIROC6 and TaiESM1 exhibit some biases of monsoonal cold surges (Section 2.4 in D7.2), the cyclogenesis of Borneo vortex is also less realistic than the nextGEMS models: MIROC6 overestimates the frequency over the South China Sea and a high density seems to concentrate relatively northward (Fig. 13e). Conversely, TaiESM1 shows a westward shift of the occurrence, especially, higher density over the Malay Peninsula than ERA5 and other models (Fig. 13f). MRI-ESM2-0, whose cold surges overperform those of other CMIP6 models, reproduces the NE-SW distribution of vortex occurrence along the northwestern coast of the Borneo Island (Fig. 13g).

Another important aspect of Borneo vortex is its intense rainfall and distribution around the vortex centre. A semi-idealized Borneo vortex by Koseki et al. (2014) shows a comma-shaped rainband in the northern sector around the vortex. This is caused by a strong convergence zone created by the northeasterly (background) cold surge flow and the cyclonic flow of the Borneo

Figure 12: Projected changes in lifetime-maximum intensity and intensification rates in for IB-TrACS observations (grey) and nextGEMS simulations. Shown are the (a) annual-mean frequency distribution of lifetime-maximum intensity; (b) projected annual frequency change under SSP3-7.0 for (dashed line) lifetime-maximum intensity timesteps and (solid line) all timesteps; (c) annual-mean frequency distribution of 24-hour intensity change (i.e., positive = intensifying; negative = weakening); and (d) projected annual frequency change of 24-hour intensity change under SSP3-7.0. Intensification rates defined as RI (i.e., $\leq 15.4 \text{ ms}^{-1} 24\text{h}^{-1}$) are to the right of the dashed, grey line in (c). Note that all timesteps are used in (c), so missing data in IB-TrACS result in the significant model–observation difference at low (i.e., near-zero) intensity changes. Performing this analysis for a region where fewer missing data exist in IBTrACS, such as the North Atlantic, results in better model–observation agreement (not shown).

Figure 13: Occurrence density of Borneo vortex for ERA5 and the models at $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ grid cell in December. Note that the ICON models have 30 years of data, and AWI-CM3-HR has 10 years of data for this analysis, while other models and ERA5 have 35 years. The Borneo vortex is detected within the red box of the geographical map.

vortex. Because of a composited rainfall and $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ interpolated data, the distribution of the rainfall around the vortex centre is not very sharp. Still, rainfall dominates in the northern sector of the vortex in ERA5 (Fig. 14a). In particular, the maximum to the northwest of the centre would correspond to a comma head of the rainfall band. In contrast, the rainfall is weak in the southern sector of the vortex. This is associated with a divergent field where monsoonal cold surge flows southward and south-eastward, and the cyclonic circulation is eastward (Koseki et al. (2014)). Such rainfall distribution is successfully simulated in the nextGEMS ESMS (Figs. 14b, c, and d). The ICON models tend to overrate the comma-head rainfall, but the north-eastward extension of the intense rainfall is well captured (Figs. 14b and c). In terms of magnitude, AWI-CM3-HR is more realistic than the ICON models (Fig. 14d). While the CMIP6 models can reproduce the occurrence of Borneo vortices to some extent, there appears to be some difficulty in simulating the horizontal structure properly. For example, MIROC6 extensively overestimates precipitation's core around the vortex centre (Fig. 14e). MIROC6 simulates too intense rainfall during strong surges. The core of the composited rainfall, moreover, is located to the north of the vortex centre, and it is indicated that the structure of the rainband around vortices is not well reproduced. MRI-ESM2-0 has a similar rainfall pattern to MIROC6 in terms of horizontal pattern (Fig. 14g). While the magnitude of the rainfall is realistic (because the simulated strong surges by MRI-ESM2-0 outperform other models), the core shifts eastward compared to ERA5 and the nextGEMS ESMS. The rainfall simulated by TaiESM1 has a comparable amplitude to ERA5 (slightly overestimated). Still, the core of the precipitation seems to move more southward

Figure 14: Composite of relative vorticity (s-1) and hourly precipitation (mm/hour) around the centres of Borneo vortices (denoted as C) for the reanalysis and ESMs.

around the vortex: while ERA5 and other models show an asymmetric structure in meridional direction, TaiESM1's precipitation around the vortex is more symmetric north-southward (Fig. 14f). This can be caused by westward-biased strong surges in TaiESM1 (Section 4.2 of D7.1).

3.5 Predicting Tropical Cyclones in the Western North Pacific under Current and Future Warming Climates (Hsin-Chien Liang, Wan-Ling Tseng, Chaoan Chen, Sho Arakane, Academia Sinica, Taiwan)

Tropical cyclones (TCs) are among the most powerful and destructive natural phenomena, posing substantial risks to coastal regions and playing a significant role in the global climate system. The Western North Pacific (WNP) is the most active TC basin globally, making accurate simulations of TC behavior in this region essential for improving future projections and enhancing disaster preparedness. Understanding how well storm-resolving models reproduce TC characteristics under both current and warming climates is key to refining climate risk assessments. This study employs two cutting-edge global storm-resolving models—the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts and the Icosahedral Nonhydrostatic (ICON) model from the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology. These models, developed under the Next-Generation Earth Modeling Systems (nextGEMS) project, run at high spatial resolutions (28 to 2.8 km) to resolve TCs with greater detail and realism.

The models reproduce the observed spatial distribution of TC track density in the WNP with

Figure 15: TC track density in the western North Pacific. (a) Observed track density from IB-TrACS. (b, c) Historical simulations from the IFS and ICON models, respectively. (d, e) Future (warming scenario) simulations from IFS and ICON. (f, g) Projected changes in TC track density (future minus historical) for IFS and ICON, respectively. Units are number of tracks per $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ grid box per year. Warm colors in (a–e) indicate higher track density, while in (f, g), brown and green shading indicate decreases and increases in TC track density, respectively.

reasonable fidelity (Fig. 15). Both IFS and ICON simulate the climatological pattern of frequent TC tracks around the Philippines and South China Sea. Under warming (SSP3-7.0) scenario, the models project a modest shift and regional redistribution in track densities, with some areas experiencing increased activity. The models accurately capture the seasonal evolution of TCs (Fig. 16), with peak activity in late summer (August–September). Future simulations reveal a tendency toward stronger storms, with intensified surface wind speeds and reduced central pressure. The frequency of intense TCs (categories 3–5) also increases under warming, despite overall TC counts remaining relatively stable. However, there are differences between IFS and ICON. For example, IFS projects increased tropical storms (category TS), whereas ICON projects a reduction, indicating some model uncertainty. The ratio of TC-related precipitation to total rainfall shows strong seasonality and latitudinal variation (Fig. 17). Observations and models agree that TC rainfall is concentrated between 10° – 30° N during the wet seasons. Under warming scenario, ICON and IFS suggest a delayed peak in TC rainfall contribution, shifting into late autumn, which may have implications for seasonal water resources and flood risks.

Storm-resolving models demonstrate substantial improvements in simulating the key characteristics of tropical cyclones, including their spatial distribution, seasonal progression, intensity spectrum, and rainfall contributions. Under warming scenario, these models consistently project stronger cyclones and altered rainfall patterns, particularly a delay in peak TC precipitation. These insights highlight the growing capability of high-resolution modeling frameworks in representing complex mesoscale interactions, offering a promising path for improving future projections of TC-related hazards and informing adaptation strategies for vulnerable regions.

Figure 16: TC characteristics over the western North Pacific (WNP) for the annual mean (ANN) during 1985–2014. (a) Monthly mean TC counts (≥ 34 knots) from observations (IBTrACS) and various model simulations, including IFS and ICON under historical (hist) and warming scenario (SSP3-7.0) conditions. (b) TC central pressure versus surface wind speed relationship, comparing observed data (IBTrACS) with model simulations. (c) Annual mean TC counts categorized by intensity, following the Saffir-Simpson scale: tropical storms (TS; 34–64 kt), and categories 1–5. Bars represent different datasets: IFS-SSP3-7.0, IFS-hist, ICON-SSP3-7.0, ICON-hist, and IBTrACS. This figure illustrates the seasonal cycle, intensity distribution, and structural characteristics of TCs as simulated by different models and compared to observations.

Figure 17: Zonal-mean ratio of TC rainfall to total rainfall averaged over 110°E–145°E, shown as a function of latitude and pentad (5-day period). (a) Observational estimate, and (b–e) model simulations from IFS and ICON under historical (hist) and warming scenario (SSP3-7.0) conditions. Vertical dashed lines indicate seasonal divisions: Winter, Spring, 1st wet season, 2nd wet season, and Fall. The color shading represents the percentage contribution of TC rainfall to total rainfall, with warmer colors indicating a higher contribution. The figure highlights the seasonal and latitudinal variability in TC-related precipitation across different models and scenarios.

3.6 Additional topics originally intended for inclusion in this report

3.6.1 Intensity and frequency dependence on large-scale environment in ICON (Mikael Karvinen, MPI-M)

This work could not be reported. However, the work is intended to be submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

3.6.2 Sea-surface cooling composite analysis (Arjun Kumar, MPI-M)

This work could not be reported (due to a change in the employment of the above-named person). However, the work is intended to be submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed journal. **FAO internal reviewers: Arjun shared some results with this report's lead author several months ago, which could be included, if required.**

3.6.3 Ocean responses to tropical cyclones (Charles Pelletier, ECMWF)

This work could not be reported. However, the work is intended to be submitted for publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

3.6.4 West Africa variability (Elsa Mohino, Universidad Complutense de Madrid)

This work has been included in D7.1.

4 Deviations

4.1 Apparent effect of spinup on global TC count in IFS (Alex Baker, University of Reading)

A timeseries of global TC count simulated by IFS in cycle 4 (production simulations), reveals an approximately constant TC count over the historical period that is consistent with observations. However, the first 5 years of the scenario simulations exhibit lower counts, which then jump rapidly around the year 2025. This apparently only affects weaker TCs, as this jump is not evident in the number of major (category 3 to 5) systems (Fig. 18). This reveals a likely effect of the relatively short spinup persisting at the beginning of the scenario simulation. This lead to some analyses of IFS production simulations excluding the first five years of the scenario, and this will continue to be necessary for future analysis of these model outputs. Potentially, this could be mitigated by an experimental design that allows for a continuous historical and scenario simulation, with appropriate forcings introduced in a given year (e.g., 2020), but without requiring separate spinup for the future integration. This is an open question.

Figure 18: Annual-mean, global n_{TC} timeseries from nextGEMS IFS simulations. Shown are (open black markers) all TCs, (filled black markers) major (category 3–5 equivalent) TCs, and (red stars) the percentage of major TCs. Historical and scenario simulations are indicated by the solid and dash lines, respectively.

5 Conclusion

Here, a cross section of tropical cyclone-related research from the nextGEMS community has been summarised. The key findings presented in this report are:

1. nextGEMS simulations show good qualitative agreement with observations in terms of the total TC frequency and the seasonality globally, although biases exist in particular basins. For example, the western North Pacific is well represented. However, North Atlantic frequency is underestimated in IFS and overestimated in ICON.
2. A dedicated case study of a TC–eddy interaction shows that a simulated subsurface warm-core ocean eddy, which could not be detected from the sea-surface temperature, can increase TC intensity by one category on the Saffir-Simpson scale.
3. TCs interacting with cold-core eddies exhibit significantly lower intensities and intensification rates, but TCs encountering warm-core eddies tend to show higher intensities and intensification rates.
4. nextGEMS models capture realistic TC intensification rates. Composite intensification in IFS at 4.4 km and ICON at 5 km mimic IBTrACS observations closely, and this is sensitive to resolution as well as models' treatment of deep convection. Particularly noteworthy is the ability of IFS at 4.4 km in capturing RI, which remains challenging in numerical weather prediction (Majumdar et al. (2023)), and that it does so at a frequency close to that observed. This improvement is related in part to the use of reduced cloud-base mass flux, which increases RI ratio significantly versus explicit convection. In this simulation, deep convection may be considered partially parameterised, and this, we hypothesise, prevents convection from being triggered too abruptly in the presence of instability, which can occur in simulations with explicit convection. This may allow convective available potential energy to build before convection occurs. Testing this, and evaluating its importance versus that of resolution, is necessary future work.
5. The simulated relationship between intensification rate and TC size at ≤ 5 km resolution resembles the observed relationship, indicating that GSRMs may help understand what role, if any, size has in determining intensification rate. Physical understanding of the size–intensification relationship is developing (Chan and Chan, 2018). As simulated horizontal inner-core structure is constrained by resolution, TC circulation becomes more realistic at finer resolution, with reduced RMW (Majumdar et al. (2023)) and off-centre vertical velocity maxima (Moon et al. (2020)). Sparks and Toumi (2022) related a TC's p_{min} tendency to the ratio of its RMW and in-flow or outflow speed, finding that this relationship is particularly important for higher observed intensification rates. This implies an upper limit on intensification rate for a given RMW and indicates that not capturing realistic RMW prevents models from simulating realistic intensification. Potentially, inner-core size is a physical constraint preventing coarse-resolution models from capturing observed intensification rates—and RI, observed cases of which frequently exhibit a 'pinhole eye' (Olander and Velden (2007)).
6. Under SSP3-7.0, frequency changes of TCs up to category-four-equivalent intensity are small, but TCs with peak intensities of at least 50 ms^{-1} (equivalent to category five) exhibit a marked increase in frequency. This result is qualitatively similar to existing findings (Knutson

et al. (2020)).

7. Under warming, nextGEMS models project stronger western North Pacific TCs and altered TC-rainfall patterns, particularly a delay in peak TC precipitation. It will be important to build on this result in future work to explore sensitivities to model physics as well as alternative scenarios.

8. The impact of ocean spinup on basin-scale and global TC activity warrants further investigation. First to address the issue of short spinup affecting weaker TC frequency and then to address the potential impact on climate projections.

5.1 Outlook

We anticipate that other TC processes for which intensification rate plays a significant role may be simulated more realistically by GSRMs, particularly air–sea interactions, such as those between ocean eddies and developing TCs (Zhang et al. (2020)), and TC-related precipitation extrema (Lamers et al. (2023)). In our analysis, intensification rate is insensitive to ocean resolution, but previous case-study work, for example, found stronger cold wakes with increased ocean resolution (Polichtchouk et al. (2022)). Further studies of TC interactions with the ocean mixed layer at high-resolution will be valuable. Ongoing efforts to integrate GSRMs over multiple decades (e.g., as part of related projects, such as the Climate Adaptation Digital Twin of Destination Earth and EERIE] will allow these questions to be explored more fully, advancing our understanding of the role of intense TCs in the climate system and of their behaviour in a warming climate.

6 References

- Aarons, Z. S., S. J. Camargo, J. D. O. Strong, and H. Murakami (2021). “Tropical Cyclone Characteristics in the MERRA-2 Reanalysis and AMIP Simulations”. In: *Earth and Space Science* 8.3. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EA001415>, e2020EA001415. ISSN: 2333-5084. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EA001415>.
- Baker, A. J., B. Vannière, and P. L. Vidale (2024). “On the Realism of Tropical Cyclone Intensification in Global Storm-Resolving Climate Models”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 51.17, e2024GL109841. ISSN: 0094-8276. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL109841>.
- Bhatia, K., A. Baker, W. Yang, G. Vecchi, T. Knutson, H. Murakami, J. Kossin, K. Hodges, K. Dixon, B. Bronselaer, and C. Whitlock (2022). “A potential explanation for the global increase in tropical cyclone rapid intensification”. In: *Nature Communications* 13.1, p. 6626. ISSN: 2041-1723. DOI: [10.1038/s41467-022-34321-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-34321-6).
- Chan, K. T. F. and J. C. L. Chan (2018). “The outer-core wind structure of tropical cyclones”. In: *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan* 96.4. Export Date: 13 February 2024; Cited By: 16, pp. 297–315. DOI: [10.2151/jmsj.2018-042](https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2018-042).
- Chang, C.-P., C.-H. Liu, and H.-C. Kuo (2003). “Typhoon Vamei: An equatorial tropical cyclone formation”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 30.3, p. 1150. ISSN: 1944-8007. DOI: [10.1029/2002GL016365](https://doi.org/10.1029/2002GL016365).
- Davis, C. A. (2018). “Resolving Tropical Cyclone Intensity in Models”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 45.4, pp. 2082–2087. ISSN: 0094-8276. DOI: [10.1002/2017GL076966](https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL076966).
- Dulac, W., J. Cattiaux, F. Chauvin, S. Bourdin, and S. Fromang (2024). “Assessing the representation of tropical cyclones in ERA5 with the CNRM tracker”. In: *Climate Dynamics* 62.1, pp. 223–238. ISSN: 1432-0894. DOI: [10.1007/s00382-023-06902-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-023-06902-8).
- Elsner, J. B. (2020). “Continued Increases in the Intensity of Strong Tropical Cyclones”. In: *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 101.8, E1301–E1303. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0338.1>.
- García-Franco, J. L., O. Gómez-Ramos, and C. Domínguez (2024). “Hurricane Otis: the costliest and strongest hurricane at landfall on record in Mexico”. In: *Weather* 79.6, pp. 182–184. ISSN: 0043-1656. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/wea.4555>.
- Hohenegger, C., P. Korn, L. Linardakis, R. Redler, R. Schnur, P. Adamidis, J. Bao, S. Bastin, M. Behraves, M. Bergemann, J. Biercamp, H. Bockelmann, R. Brokopf, N. Brüggemann, L. Casaroli, F. Chegini, G. Datsaris, M. Esch, G. George, M. Giorgetta, O. Gutjahr, H. Haak, M. Hanke, T. Ilyina, T. Jahns, J. Jungclaus, M. Kern, D. Klocke, L. Kluft, T. Kölling, L. Kornbluh, S. Kosukhin, C. Kroll, J. Lee, T. Mauritsen, C. Mehlmann, T. Mieslinger, A. K. Naumann, L. Paccini, A. Peinado, D. S. Praturi, D. Putrasahan, S. Rast, T. Riddick, N. Roeber, H. Schmidt, U. Schulzweida, F. Schütte, H. Segura, R. Shevchenko, V. Singh, M. Specht, C. C. Stephan, J. S. von Storch, R. Vogel, C. Wengel, M. Winkler, F. Ziemann, J. Marotzke, and B. Stevens (2023). “ICON-Sapphire: simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales”. In: *Geosci. Model Dev.* 16.2. GMD, pp. 779–811. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: [10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023).
- Jing, R., S. Heft-Neal, D. R. Chavas, M. Griswold, Z. Wang, A. Clark-Ginsberg, D. Guha-Sapir, E. Bendavid, and Z. Wagner (2024). “Global population profile of tropical cyclone exposure from 2002 to 2019”. In: *Nature* 626.7999, pp. 549–554. ISSN: 1476-4687. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-023-06963-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06963-z).

- Judt, F., D. Klocke, R. Rios-Berrios, B. Vannière, F. Ziemer, L. Auger, J. Biercamp, C. Bretherton, X. Chen, P. Düben, C. Hohenegger, M. Khairoutdinov, C. Kodama, L. Kornblueh, S.-J. Lin, M. Nakano, P. Neumann, W. Putman, N. Röber, M. Roberts, M. Satoh, R. Shibuya, B. Stevens, P. L. Vidale, N. Wedi, and L. Zhou (2021). “Tropical Cyclones in Global Storm-Resolving Models”. In: *Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan. Ser. II* 99.3, pp. 579–602. DOI: [10.2151/jmsj.2021-029](https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2021-029).
- Kaplan, J. and M. DeMaria (2003). “Large-Scale Characteristics of Rapidly Intensifying Tropical Cyclones in the North Atlantic Basin”. In: *Weather and Forecasting* 18.6, pp. 1093–1108. ISSN: 0882-8156. DOI: [10.1175/1520-0434\(2003\)018<1093:LCORIT>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0434(2003)018<1093:LCORIT>2.0.CO;2).
- Klotzbach, P. J., M. M. Bell, S. G. Bowen, E. J. Gibney, K. R. Knapp, and I. Schreck Carl J. (2020). “Surface Pressure a More Skillful Predictor of Normalized Hurricane Damage than Maximum Sustained Wind”. In: *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 101.6, E830–E846. ISSN: 0003-0007. DOI: [10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0062.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0062.1).
- Klotzbach, P. J., K. M. Wood, C. J. Schreck III, S. G. Bowen, C. M. Patricola, and M. M. Bell (2022). “Trends in Global Tropical Cyclone Activity: 1990–2021”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 49.6. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL095774>, e2021GL095774. ISSN: 0094-8276. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL095774>.
- Knutson, T., S. J. Camargo, J. C. L. Chan, K. Emanuel, C.-H. Ho, J. Kossin, M. Mohapatra, M. Satoh, M. Sugi, K. Walsh, and L. Wu (2020). “Tropical Cyclones and Climate Change Assessment: Part II: Projected Response to Anthropogenic Warming”. In: *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 101.3, E303–E322. DOI: [10.1175/BAMS-D-18-0194.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-18-0194.1).
- Koldunov, N., T. Kölling, X. Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, T. Rackow, R. Redler, D. Sidorenko, K.-H. Wieners, and F. A. Ziemer (2023). “nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 3 simulations for ICON and IFS”. In: *World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ*. DOI: [10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3](https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3).
- Koseki, S., T.-Y. Koh, and C.-K. Teo (2014). “Borneo vortex and mesoscale convective rainfall”. In: *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 14.9, pp. 4539–4562. ISSN: 1680-7316. DOI: [10.5194/acp-14-4539-2014](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-14-4539-2014).
- Kreussler, P., L.-P. Caron, S. Wild, S. Loosveldt Tomas, F. Chauvin, M.-P. Moine, M. J. Roberts, Y. Ruprich-Robert, J. Seddon, S. Valcke, B. Vannière, and P. L. Vidale (2021). “Tropical Cyclone Integrated Kinetic Energy in an Ensemble of HighResMIP Simulations”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 48.5, e2020GL090963. ISSN: 0094-8276. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL090963>.
- Kumar, A. U., N. Brüggemann, R. K. Smith, and J. Marotzke (2022). “Response of a tropical cyclone to a subsurface ocean eddy and the role of boundary layer dynamics”. In: *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society* 148.742, pp. 378–402. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4210>.
- Lamers, A., S. Devi. S, M. Sharma, R. Berg, J. M. Gálvez, Z. Yu, T. Kriat, S. Cardoso, D. Grant, and L. A. Moron (2023). “Forecasting tropical cyclone rainfall and flooding hazards and impacts”. In: *Tropical Cyclone Research and Review* 12.2, pp. 100–112. ISSN: 2225-6032. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tcr.2023.06.005>.
- Lang, S., D. Schepers, and M. Rodwell (2023). “IFS upgrade brings many improvements and unifies medium-range resolutions”. In: *ECMWF Newsletter* 176, pp. 21–28. DOI: [doi:10.21957/slk503fs2i](https://doi.org/10.21957/slk503fs2i).

- Majumdar, S. J., L. Magnusson, P. Bechtold, J. R. Bidlot, and J. D. Doyle (2023). “Advanced Tropical Cyclone Prediction Using the Experimental Global ECMWF and Operational Regional COAMPS-TC Systems”. In: *Monthly Weather Review* 151.8, pp. 2029–2048. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-22-0236.1>.
- Moon, Y., D. Kim, S. J. Camargo, A. A. Wing, A. H. Sobel, H. Murakami, K. A. Reed, E. Scoccimarro, G. A. Vecchi, M. F. Wehner, C. M. Zarzycki, and M. Zhao (2020). “Azimuthally Averaged Wind and Thermodynamic Structures of Tropical Cyclones in Global Climate Models and Their Sensitivity to Horizontal Resolution”. In: *Journal of Climate* 33.4, pp. 1575–1595. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-19-0172.1>.
- Olander, T. L. and C. S. Velden (2007). “The Advanced Dvorak Technique: Continued Development of an Objective Scheme to Estimate Tropical Cyclone Intensity Using Geostationary Infrared Satellite Imagery”. In: *Weather and Forecasting* 22.2, pp. 287–298. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/WAF975.1>.
- Polichtchouk, I., K. Mogensen, I. Hadade, S. Hatfield, and V. Anantharaj (2022). “Greater atmospheric resolution improves prediction of tropical cyclones”. In: *ECMWF Newsletter* 172, pp. 8–9.
- Rackow, T., X. Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, T. Becker, S. Milinski, I. Sandu, R. Aguridan, P. Bechtold, S. Beyer, J. Bidlot, S. Boussetta, W. Deconinck, M. Diamantakis, P. Dueben, E. Dutra, R. Forbes, R. Ghosh, H. F. Goessling, I. Hadade, J. Hegewald, T. Jung, S. Keeley, L. Kluff, N. Koldunov, A. Koldunov, T. Kölling, J. Kousal, C. Kühnlein, P. Maciel, K. Mogensen, T. Quintino, I. Polichtchouk, B. Reuter, D. Sármany, P. Scholz, D. Sidorenko, J. Streffing, B. Sützl, D. Takasuka, S. Tietsche, M. Valentini, B. Vannière, N. Wedi, L. Zampieri, and F. Ziemann (2025). “Multi-year simulations at kilometre scale with the Integrated Forecasting System coupled to FESOM2.5 and NEMOV3.4”. In: *Geosci. Model Dev.* 18.1, pp. 33–69. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: [10.5194/gmd-18-33-2025](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-18-33-2025).
- Roberts, M. J., J. Camp, J. Seddon, P. L. Vidale, K. Hodges, B. Vanniere, J. Mecking, R. Haarsma, A. Bellucci, E. Scoccimarro, L.-P. Caron, F. Chauvin, L. Terray, S. Valcke, M.-P. Moine, D. Putrasahan, C. Roberts, R. Senan, C. Zarzycki, and P. Ullrich (2020). “Impact of Model Resolution on Tropical Cyclone Simulation Using the HighResMIP-PRIMAVERA Multimodel Ensemble”. In: *Journal of Climate* 33.7, pp. 2557–2583. DOI: [10.1175/jcli-d-19-0639.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/jcli-d-19-0639.1).
- Satoh, M., B. Stevens, F. Judt, M. Khairoutdinov, S.-J. Lin, W. M. Putman, and P. Düben (2019). “Global Cloud-Resolving Models”. In: *Current Climate Change Reports* 5.3, pp. 172–184. ISSN: 2198-6061. DOI: [10.1007/s40641-019-00131-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40641-019-00131-0).
- Schenkel, B. A., N. Lin, D. Chavas, G. A. Vecchi, M. Oppenheimer, and A. Brammer (2018). “Lifetime Evolution of Outer Tropical Cyclone Size and Structure as Diagnosed from Reanalysis and Climate Model Data”. In: *Journal of Climate* 31.19, pp. 7985–8004. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-17-0630.1>.
- Schreck III, C. J., K. R. Knapp, and J. P. Kossin (2014). “The Impact of Best Track Discrepancies on Global Tropical Cyclone Climatologies using IBTrACS”. In: *Monthly Weather Review* 142.10, pp. 3881–3899. DOI: [10.1175/mwr-d-14-00021.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/mwr-d-14-00021.1).
- Segura, H. et al. (2025). “nextGEMS: entering the era of kilometer-scale Earth system modeling”. In: DOI: [10.5194/egusphere-2025-509](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-509).

- Sparks, N. and R. Toumi (2022). “The Dependence of Tropical Cyclone Pressure Tendency on Size”. In: *Geophysical Research Letters* 49.19, e2022GL098926. ISSN: 0094-8276. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL098926>.
- Tam, H.-f., C.-w. Choy, and W.-k. Wong (2021). “Development of objective forecast guidance on tropical cyclone rapid intensity change”. In: *Meteorological Applications* 28.2, e1981. ISSN: 1350-4827. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/met.1981>.
- Tatebe, H., T. Ogura, T. Nitta, Y. Komuro, K. Ogochi, T. Takemura, K. Sudo, M. Sekiguchi, M. Abe, F. Saito, M. Chikira, S. Watanabe, M. Mori, N. Hirota, Y. Kawatani, T. Mochizuki, K. Yoshimura, K. Takata, R. Oishi, D. Yamazaki, T. Suzuki, M. Kurogi, T. Kataoka, M. Wanatabe, and M. Kimoto (2019). “Description and basic evaluation of simulated mean state, internal variability, and climate sensitivity in MIROC6”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 12.7, pp. 2727–2765. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: [10.5194/gmd-12-2727-2019](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-2727-2019).
- Trabing, B. C. and M. M. Bell (2020). “Understanding Error Distributions of Hurricane Intensity Forecasts during Rapid Intensity Changes”. In: *Weather and Forecasting* 35.6, pp. 2219–2234. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/WAF-D-19-0253.1>.
- Ullrich, P. A. and C. M. Zarzycki (2017). “TempestExtremes: a framework for scale-insensitive pointwise feature tracking on unstructured grids”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 10.3. GMD <https://www.geosci-model-dev.net/10/1069/2017/gmd-10-1069-2017.pdf>, pp. 1069–1090. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: [10.5194/gmd-10-1069-2017](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-1069-2017).
- Ullrich, P. A., C. M. Zarzycki, E. E. McClenny, M. C. Pinheiro, A. M. Stansfield, and K. A. Reed (2021). “TempestExtremes v2.1: a community framework for feature detection, tracking, and analysis in large datasets”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 14.8. GMD <https://gmd.copernicus.org/article/view/5023-2021>, pp. 5023–5048. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: [10.5194/gmd-14-5023-2021](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-5023-2021).
- Vannire, B., M. Roberts, P. L. Vidale, K. Hodges, M.-E. Demory, L.-P. Caron, E. Scoccimarro, L. Terray, and R. Senan (2020). “The Moisture Budget of Tropical Cyclones in HighResMIP Models: Large-Scale Environmental Balance and Sensitivity to Horizontal Resolution”. In: *Journal of Climate* 33.19, pp. 8457–8474. ISSN: 0894-8755. DOI: [10.1175/JCLI-D-19-0999.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-19-0999.1).
- Wang, Y.-C., H.-H. Hsu, C.-A. Chen, W.-L. Tseng, P.-C. Hsu, C.-W. Lin, Y.-L. Chen, L.-C. Jiang, Y.-C. Lee, H.-C. Liang, W.-M. Chang, W.-L. Lee, and C.-J. Shiu (2021). “Performance of the Taiwan Earth System Model in Simulating Climate Variability Compared With Observations and CMIP6 Model Simulations”. In: *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* 13.7, e2020MS002353. ISSN: 1991-9603. DOI: [10.1029/2020MS002353](https://doi.org/10.1029/2020MS002353).
- World Meteorological Organization (2021). *WMO Atlas of Mortality and Economic Losses from Weather, Climate and Water Extremes (1970–2019)*. Generic. DOI: <https://library.wmo.int/idurl/4/57564>.
- Wu, L., R. Wang, and X. Feng (2018). “Dominant Role of the Ocean Mixed Layer Depth in the Increased Proportion of Intense Typhoons During 1980–2015”. In: *Earth’s Future* 6.11, pp. 1518–1527. ISSN: 2328-4277. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018EF000973>.
- Xu, J. and Y. Wang (2015). “A Statistical Analysis on the Dependence of Tropical Cyclone Intensification Rate on the Storm Intensity and Size in the North Atlantic”. In: *Weather and Forecasting* 30.3, pp. 692–701. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/WAF-D-14-00141.1>.
- Yukimoto, S., K. H., T. Koshio, O. N., Y. K., S. Urakawa, H. Tsujino, H. Deushi, T. Tanaka, M. Hosaka, S. Yabu, H. Yoshimura, E. Shindo, R. Mizuta, A. Obata, Y. Adabi, and M. Ishii (2019). “The Meteorological Research Institute Earth System Model Version 2.0, MRI-

- ESM2.0: Description and Basic Evaluation of the Physical Component”. In: *Journal of The Meteorological Society of Japan* 97.5, pp. 931–965. ISSN: 2186-9057. DOI: [10.2151/jmsj.2019-051](https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2019-051).
- Zarzycki, C. M. (2016). “Tropical Cyclone Intensity Errors Associated with Lack of Two-Way Ocean Coupling in High-Resolution Global Simulations”. In: *Journal of Climate* 29.23, pp. 8589–8610. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0273.1>.
- Zhang, Y., Z. Zhang, D. Chen, B. Qiu, and W. Wang (2020). “Strengthening of the Kuroshio current by intensifying tropical cyclones”. In: *Science* 368.6494. doi: 10.1126/science.aax5758, pp. 988–993. DOI: [10.1126/science.aax5758](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aax5758).